

Results of regression analyses to explain yield and pest intensity in farmers' fields at rainfed lowland sites in Vietnam and northeast Thailand.^a

Dependent variable	Variable in equation	Slope	Standard error of slope	Beta value
YIELD	Y_t	.616	.044	1.033
	GPEST	-.332	.073	-.333
	constant	2.763	.146	
	$R^2 = .72; n = 93$			
GPEST	SAND	-.021	.004	-.507
	Y_t	.342	.071	.571
	$Y_t * P * K$	-.127	.036	-.355
	constant	2.402	.263	
	$R^2 = .62; n = 93$			

^aYIELD = yield in t/ha; Y_t = target yield; GPEST = pest intensity on generative plant organs and/or whole tillers; SAND = % soil sand content; P = ppm available soil P; K = meq K/100 g soil. All variables in the equations are significant at $P = 0.001$ according to *T*-test. Both regression models are significant at $p = 0.0001$ according to *F*-test.

generative plant organs and/or whole tillers was computed: $GPEST = \ln\{[1 - (1 - x_1/100)(1 - x_2/100)...(1 - x_n/100)]100 + 1\}$, where $x_1 \dots x_n$ = % maximum severity level of the respective disease or pest damage type. Pest damage types and diseases considered for computing GPEST were panicle blast, dirty panicle, stem rot, foot rot, tungro virus, false smut, other panicle damage, stem borer deadhearts and whiteheads, and cut tillers due to other pests.

In multivariate regression analyses, yield variation was explained by Y_t (target yield) and GPEST with $R^2 = 0.72$. Y_t had a much greater relative value for predicting yield than did GPEST (see table). Variability of GPEST could be explained by parameters of soil fertility and water-holding capacity such as soil sand content (SAND), Y_t , and a term describing interaction among Y_t , soil phosphorus (P), and soil potassium content (K) with $R^2 = 0.62$. When predicted values are plotted vs actual

values, data points for the different sites blend fairly well into a homogeneous data cloud along the 1:1 line (see figure).

The results indicate that it is possible to quantify rice yield expectations for rainfed lowland areas based on parameters that characterize soil fertility corresponding to physiological potential yield, although parameterization of Y_t might need further adjustment and the role of water problems needs investigation and appropriate consideration. Yield expectations can be further adjusted for pest damage effects through relatively simple single equation-type models. Pest damage expectations might be quantifiable based on parameters of soil fertility and water-holding capacity, because high soil N (and in some cases drought stress) increases the susceptibility of the rice crop to pest attacks.

Further analyses will aim to identify key biotic constraints for higher yields, develop simple yet robust rules for predicting the proneness of sites for

Actual YIELD (t/ha)

Actual GPEST (% ln [y+1])

a) Observed yield (YIELD) and b) pest intensity during the generative phase (GPEST) vs values estimated by MRA for farmers' fields at rainfed lowland site ^a in northeast Thailand and Vietnam ^b.

^aSites: Thailand 1= Khon Kaen, 2= Phai Mai, 3= Sakon Nakhon, 4= Ubon; Vietnam 5= Bac Lieu, 6= Ca Mau, 7= Long An, 8= Soc Trang. \$ = multiple occurrence of data points. ^bSee Table 1 for regression equations and definition of variables.

specific pest-loss problems, and define agroecological domains for extrapolation of knowledge and technology for disease management in rainfed lowland rice. ■

Genetic manipulation of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*

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Introduction of plasmid DNA into *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo),

the rice bacterial blight pathogen, can be routinely and efficiently achieved by electrotransformation or by conjugation using a biparental mating system. Mobilizable plasmids with broad-host range, such as pUFRO27, pUFRO47, pHM1(cosmid), pUFRO34(cosmid), pUFRO43(cosmid), and pLAFR3(cosmid) are convenient vectors that are compatible with Xoo. Electrotransformation requires

a costly instrument, the electro-porator, but is fast, easy, and good for small-scale cloning experiments. Biparental matings between Xoo and *E. coli* strain S17-1, which has a mobilization gene in the chromosome, do not require expensive equipment and are excellent for large-scale experiments, such as screening a genomic library. With this system, a helper plasmid is not needed to mobi-

lize the vector, which simplifies manipulation. Generally, the transconjugation frequencies obtained after biparental mating are 10^2 - to 10^5 -fold higher than those observed after both electrotransformation (Table 1) and triparental matings.

The presence of restriction-modification (R-M) systems in Xoo strains influences transformation and conjugation frequencies (Table 1). Xoo contains at least two R-M systems (*XorI* and *XorII*). Genomic DNA from Xoo that contains the *XorI* R-M system is not digested by the endonuclease *PstI* (*XorI* isoschizomer). Genomic DNA from Xoo that contains the *XorII* R-M system is not digested by either *XorII* or *PvuII* (isoschizomer of *XorII*). The Xoo strains with neither R-M system (*XorI*/*XorII*⁻ phenotype) are better recipients than strains having one or both of the R-M systems. Strains with *XorI*/*XorII*⁺ phenotype are better recipients than those with *XorI*⁺/*XorII*⁻ phenotype.

We have so far been unable to introduce DNA into PXO61, which has both *XorI* and *XorII* R-M systems, by either of the two methods (Table 1). Transformation and conjugation frequencies of 5-azacytidine-resistant mutants of PXO99 (designated as PXO99A) are markedly higher when compared with those of the wild-type strain PXO99 (Table 1). 5-azacytidine has been reported to affect R-M systems, and it is possible that a third, unidentified R-M system has been affected in PXO99A. We have not yet characterized the mutation in strain PXO99A. Factors such as the growth stage of the recipient cell or culture medium and culture conditions affected transformation frequency, but the effects were not as dramatic as those imposed by the R-M systems of the recipient Xoo strain.

Both electrotransformation (Table 2) and biparental mating methods (Table 1, footnote) are sufficient to introduce plasmids into Xoo cells, which is a prerequisite for genetic studies of this agronomically important pathogen. Using these techniques, we have identified and characterized several genes controlling host-pathogen interactions (avirulence genes and hypersensitive and

Table 1. Introduction of plasmid pUFR027 into Xoo strains with different R-M systems by means of electrotransformation or biparental mating.

Strain ^a	R-M system ^b		Growth stages ^c of recipient	Transformation frequency ^d	Conjugation frequency ^e
	<i>XorI</i>	<i>XorII</i>			
PXO61	+	+	ML LL	< 10^{-9} < 10^{-9}	< 10^{-8} < 10^{-7}
8820	+	-	ML LL	5.4×10^{-8} 4.6×10^{-8}	6.8×10^{-3} 2.9×10^{-3}
PXO86	-	+	ML LL	1.6×10^{-7} 2.4×10^{-8}	2.0×10^{-1} 4.7×10^{-1}
PXO99	-	-	ML LL	1.6×10^{-6} 1.0×10^{-6}	7.6×10^{-4} 1.4×10^{-1}
PXO99A	-	-	ML	6.5×10^{-3}	7.6×10^{-1}

^aThe prefix PXO indicates Philippine strains; 8820, Korean strain; PXO99A, 5-azacytidine-resistant mutant of PXO99 that was selected for growth on 200 μ M 5-azacytidine. ^b+/-, presence/absence of R-M systems based on resistance/susceptibility, respectively, of genomic DNA to digestion with endonuclease *PstI* (isoschizomer of *XorI*) or *XorII*. ^cML/LL, mid-/late-logarithmic growth stage. Cells were grown in nutrient broth at 28 °C with shaking at 200 rpm. ^dNumber of transformants per total number of cells recovered. Av of two experiments. ^eConjugation frequencies are the number of transconjugants per total number of cells recovered after introduction of plasmid DNA by biparental mating. Recipient Xoo cells were grown in nutrient broth overnight with shaking. Cells were harvested by low-speed centrifugation and the cell number was adjusted to 10^{11} cfu/ml in sterile, distilled water. An aliquot (20 μ l) was pipetted onto a nutrient agar plate, air-dried, then incubated 1-2 h at 28 °C. *E. coli* strain S17-1 cells were cultured for 1 d on Luria Bertani agar containing appropriate antibiotics. For mating, *E. coli* cells were collected with a toothpick and mixed with the pre-incubated Xoo cells. After incubation at 28 °C for 2 d, cells were harvested, resuspended in 200 μ l of sterile water, and serially diluted (10-fold). The cells (100 μ l) were spread on agar peptone sucrose medium plates supplemented with cephalaxin (20 μ g/ml) and appropriate antibiotics. Av frequency obtained from two experiments is reported.

Table 2. Basic protocol for electrotransformation of Xoo with DNA.

Step	Procedure and technical comments
1.	Select, if possible, <i>XorII</i> ⁻ Xoo strains as recipients. <i>XorI</i> ⁺ / <i>XorII</i> ⁻ and <i>XorI</i> ⁻ / <i>XorII</i> ⁺ strains also are useful, but expect a much lower transformation frequency.
2.	Grow Xoo in 500 ml nutrient broth at 28 °C with shaking at 200 rpm until mid- to late-logarithmic growth stage (about 12-24 h).
3.	Harvest cells by low-speed centrifugation at 2 °C.
4.	Wash cells by centrifugation in 500 ml of cold sterile distilled water three times.
5.	Wash the cells in 30 ml of cold, sterile 10% glycerol.
6.	Harvest cells and resuspend in 2-3 ml of cold, sterile 10% glycerol.
7.	Dispense 70 μ l of the cells into a microcentrifuge tube that was cooled on ice; store at -80 °C until use. For immediate use, do not freeze and omit step 8.
8.	Thaw the cells on ice.
9.	Add DNA (less than 10 μ l volume) into each tube containing cells and mix well by repeated pipetting. Plasmid DNA prepared by mini-scale alkaline lysis method is pure enough to be used directly. Make sure to wash DNA with 70% ethanol before use. DNA should be resuspended in sterile distilled water and not in buffer.
10.	Transfer the cell-DNA mixture into the precooled electroporation chamber. Electroporation chambers can be reused several times by washing well with distilled water, 95% alcohol, and then 70% alcohol. The chamber should be completely dry before use. Keep the chambers at -20 °C until use.
11.	Expose cells to 600 V (amplitude) for 5 milliseconds (pulse length). These conditions are for T-100™ electroporator system (Biotechnical and Experimental Research Inc., BTX, San Diego, CA) and an electroporation chamber with 0.56-mm gap.
12.	After electroporation, recover the cells from the electroporation chamber by pipetting with 600 μ l of peptone sucrose broth.
13.	Incubate at 28 °C with shaking at 200 rpm for 4 h.
14.	Dilute and spread cells on suitable agar medium (such as peptone sucrose agar) containing appropriate antibiotics.

pathogenicity response genes), an *XorII* methylase gene, and a phosphate-binding protein gene from an Xoo genomic

library. Genetic manipulation is no longer a serious obstacle for genetic analysis of Xoo. ■